

CoARA Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment (WG ACA)

Summary and analysis of case studies on reforming academic career assessment

As part of its mapping exercise on academic career assessment initiatives, the CoARA Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment (WG ACA) developed a synthesis of national and international level initiatives for reforming academic research assessment. [Eleven case studies were selected by the WG ACA](#). The cases had to have an implementation plan targeted to organisations conducting academic career assessments (recruitment, performance evaluation and/or career progression). These initiatives needed to focus at the national or international level. A common template was sent to representatives of each initiative to collect information in a structured and comparable way. While public documentation of the initiatives could be in any language, submissions through the template had to be described in English.

The purpose of surveying the selected cases was to increase understanding of these initiatives' characteristics and learned lessons especially from the perspective of academic career assessment. This document highlights common themes and differences among the initiatives and does not intend to make valuations between them. An overview of the 11 case-studies is presented below (table 1).

Table 1. General information about the [selected initiatives](#) addressing academic career assessment

<i>Initiative and responsible institution</i>	<i>Name and year of initiation</i>	<i>Geographic scope</i>	<i>Short description</i>
ANECA (National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation)	Reforming research and academic career assessment in Spain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2023 	Spain	ANECA promotes a reform of research assessment within the framework of the commitments acquired with the Agency's accession to DORA, ARRA and CoARA.

CLACSO-FOLEC (Latin American Council of Social Sciences - Latin American Forum for Research Assessment)	Declaration of principles: a new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 2022	Latin America and the Caribbean	CLACSO-FOLEC seeks to promote implementation of its principles outlined in the declaration on responsible research assessment from and for Latin America and the Caribbean. The principles are concerned with aims of assessment, assessment processes, information systems and indicators.
CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment)	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 2022	Global	The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment sets CoARA's direction to recognise the diversity of research outputs and activities. The Agreement includes a timeframe for reforms, commitments and principles which also address CoARA members.
DORA (The American Society for Cell Biology (ASCB) as administrative entity since 2018)	The San Francisco Declaration of Research Assessment <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 2013	Global	DORA seeks to encourage best practices in the evaluation of researchers and their outputs. DORA works to convene on key issues and develop recommendations for interventions. The declaration was published in 2013 and includes 18 recommendations.
EU Charter (European Union)	The European Charter for Researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 2005 / 2023	Europe	The Charter was adopted in 2005 by the European Commission to enable the same policy standards for research careers across Europe. This was updated in December 2023 providing a framework to promote attractive and sustainable research careers in Europe.
Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (Finland)	Good Practice in Researcher Evaluation: Recommendation for Responsible Evaluation of a Researcher in Finland <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 2020	Finland	The national recommendation for researcher evaluation was developed to support more conscious decisions in evaluation processes. The working-group, built on various initiatives, such as DORA, and the structured CV template published by the Finnish National Board of Research Integrity.

Universities of the Netherlands (The Netherlands)	Recognition & Rewards Programme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020 	The Netherlands	Recognition & Rewards is a national programme of academic career assessment reform aiming for a culture change in academia. The programme strives for, among other things, greater diversity in academic career paths and the use of qualitative assessment criteria for academic outputs. Experimenting, co-creating and learning are central to the programme.
Universities Norway (Norway)	NOR-CAM – A toolbox for recognition and rewards in academic careers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021 	Norway	The process leading up to NOR-CAM started in 2019 with an Open Science working group. The toolbox includes core principles: more transparency, greater breadth, and comprehensive assessments. NOR-CAM is a framework for assessing these elements systematically for different purposes.
OR4 (UK Reproducibility Network, University of Bath, University of Cardiff, University of Greenwich, University of Keele, University of Newcastle, University of Reading, University of Surrey)	Open and Responsible Researcher Reward and Recognition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021 	United Kingdom	OR4 is part of the UK's Open Research Programme and supports the implementation in higher education and research institutions of responsible assessment policies and practices. The project will achieve its objectives through an implementation toolkit and by supporting the national community of practice.
UKRI (UK Research and Innovation)	UKRI People and Teams Action Plan 2023 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2023 	United Kingdom	UKRI's people and teams action plan sets out how the development of skilled people and teams in research and innovation will be supported by the institution. The plan builds on – and expands – Technician Commitment and Researcher Development Concordat.
YUFE4Postdocs (University of Antwerp)	YUFE4Postdocs evaluation & selection procedure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2023 	Europe	YUFE4Postdocs is a postdoctoral training program, involving universities of the Young Universities for the Future of Europe Alliance. The program resulted in 55 researchers working under a shared theme, with projects in 4 focus areas. The selection process assessed applicants on a broad and qualitative set of criteria by two committees involving stakeholders.

1. Towards shared goals through diverse initiatives

The initiatives differ somewhat in scope and objectives

While some focus on specific issues, such as open science (OR4) or involving societal stakeholders in evaluating post-doctoral candidates (YUFE4Postdocs), others take a broader approach, encompassing multiple areas in research assessment. Their aims and aspired changes are also connected to their geographical scope, as some are primarily global or international (CoARA, DORA, EU Charter, YUFE4Postdocs, CLACSO-FOLEC), whereas others are national by nature (ANECA, Finland, The Netherlands, Norway, OR4, UKRI).

Despite these differences, the initiatives share several key principles, including recognising the diversity of academic contributions, investing in qualitative assessment, supporting the responsible use of metrics and enhancing gender equality.

The list below summarises the initiatives' main goals.

- ANECA: Creating a culture of evaluation based on the quality, relevance and impact of reduced number of contributions and respect for a wider variety of careers.
- CLACSO-FOLEC: Turning assessment principles to action and increasing knowledge of best practices and innovations in evaluation.
- CoARA: Supporting a cultural change in research assessment based on qualitative judgement, responsible use of quantitative indicators and recognition of diversity in academic work.
- DORA: Improving the way researchers are assessed for hiring, promotion, tenure, and funding decisions by advocating for less quantitative assessment.
- EU Charter: Ensuring the same standards are used for evaluating researchers across Europe, and updated charter looks to increase the attractiveness of research careers.
- Federation of Finnish Learned Societies: Developing guidelines for responsible evaluation of researchers.
- Universities of the Netherlands: Enabling a healthy and inspiring environment for academic work committed to greater diversity in career paths and assessing research by content and quality, not just by quantity or journal.

- Universities Norway: Making assessment processes more transparent and predictable and creating a framework for evaluating more systematically and diversely the spectrum of academic results and competencies.
- OR4: Supporting UK institutions' recognition of and reward for open research in their policies and processes, also contributing to societal discussion and policymaking on open research.
- UKRI: Building inclusive environments and culture that promote wellbeing and support diverse career paths and developing assessment to recognise the range of contributions to research and innovation, movement and work between disciplines, sectors, business, and academia.
- YUFE4Postdocs: Developing an approach to assess postdoctoral researchers' applications to positions in academia and to enable the involvement of societal stakeholders in the selection process.

2. Involving and targeting a broad range of actors – the initiatives' stakeholders and audiences

These initiatives engage a variety of stakeholders, including research performing organisations (e.g. higher education institutions and research institutes) and organisations that fund or otherwise support research, especially public research funders. Many initiatives also involve private foundations, learned societies or academies as stakeholders, and some involve libraries and their networks (ANECA, DORA). Beyond such initiatives, OR4 "only" has a variety of universities as its stakeholders. The initiatives' stakeholders include both organisations that have been involved in the initiatives and organisations that are members of the initiatives. ANECA distinguishes that their stakeholders include organisations that the initiative has consulted, actors that the initiative collaborates with, as well as the entire scientific community with multiple entities that have been part of the participatory processes of the initiative. The involvement of diverse stakeholders underscores the need of inclusive and participatory processes in reforming academic career assessment.

The stakeholders involved in these initiatives largely reflect their intended audiences. All initiatives target two key groups: research actors being evaluated (researchers and research organisations) and research actors conducting evaluations (e.g. research funders, higher education institutions, research centres).

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Many initiatives also engage other relevant stakeholders in the research ecosystem. These include research infrastructures (CoARA), librarians (CLACSO-FOLEC, DORA), publishers (CLACSO-FOLEC, DORA), organisations that provide metrics (DORA), and actors that influence the national or regional policies around evaluation, such as public policymakers (CLACSO-FOLEC, CoARA, DORA, Finland, OR4). Additionally, OR4 identifies leaders and managers responsible for implementing and leading strategic activities related to research assessment as important stakeholders. UKRI, however, focuses solely on research-performing organisations and funders.

All initiatives have the potential to contribute to international work on reforming research assessment. Even those with a primarily national focus (ANECA, Finland, Norway, The Netherlands, UKRI, OR4) address issues, use tools or make recommendations that could be applicable in international or other national contexts. Several of these initiatives also underline that they have potential to support developments around research assessment through engagement with CoARA. Moreover, many initiatives have drawn inspiration from earlier efforts, such as DORA and the Leiden manifesto, further illustrating the interconnected nature of academic career assessment initiatives.

DORA and CoARA, as international initiatives, have significant global potential. The EU Charter and CLACSO-FOLEC, while looking to address reform issues in their region, report having potential also beyond it. Similarly, YUFE4Postdocs sees its work as relevant to higher education institutions beyond Europe, particularly in attracting postdoc research projects with societal impact potential.

3. Recommending a more qualitative way forward

The initiatives make a number of similar recommendations on qualitative and quantitative assessment, namely underlining the need to move towards a more qualitative assessment process and criteria or to give qualitative judgements priority in assessment. For instance, using peer review in evaluation is understood as important, as is using narratives that give researchers the possibility to contextualise and explain their diverse competencies, activities, outputs and impacts for assessment purposes. Responsible use of metrics is also a recurring theme, with recommendations to abandon inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index and avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment. Furthermore, many initiatives highlight that when assessing a researcher or piece of research, it is important to make the assessment in the context of the relevant field or discipline.

When it comes to the assessment process, transparency is a central principle for several initiatives. For instance, DORA recommends being explicit about the criteria in evaluation of research or in hiring, tenure, and promotion decisions. Such recommendation is targeted to funders, research organisations, researchers and organisations that provide metrics. Finland's initiative promotes the idea that the evaluated should be able to check, as far as possible, both the data in and the results of the assessment. Furthermore, related to the assessment process, ensuring diversity and gender equality in the selection of evaluators is central for multiple initiatives.

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4. Considering all career-stages and paying attention to early career researchers

Several initiatives apply to all academic career stages (CoARA, EU Charter, Finland, Norway, The Netherlands). For instance, The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies' recommendations apply to all career stages and state that researchers should not be unfairly discriminated against on the basis of their field of research, multidisciplinary status, or career stage. Similarly, the EU Charter focuses on continuous professional development on the basis of the R1 - R4 definition of researcher stages. DORA is somewhat of an exception here since it is aimed in general to all researchers and does not specifically address the issue of career stages.

Other initiatives pay special attention to early career researchers (ANECA, CLACSO-FOLEC, OR4, UKRI, YUFE4Postdocs). In the case of UKRI, the focus is on early career researchers' participation in higher education and funding policy and strategy forums. YUFE4Postdocs targeted postdoctoral researchers in particular and looked to stimulate temporary staff to seek a more stable position within or outside academia. ANECA looks to support younger researchers' well-being by enabling earlier stabilisation of academic careers. OR4 engages early career researchers in its initiative and recognises that developing an open research track record depends on the researcher's career stage. CLACSO-FOLEC takes the perspective of inclusivity, underlining the need to better include and train early career researchers to assessment practices.

5. Supporting and recognising diversity of competencies, contributions, activities and career-paths

All initiatives promote greater diversity in assessment and academia. They seek to broaden the recognition of a more varied set of competencies, contributions and activities and/or roles in the assessment of researchers. In addition, these initiatives also aim to support diversity, for instance through developing the rewarding of researchers, and seek to consider intersectoral contributions or mobility. Most initiatives view intersectorality as researchers' contributions to or participation in communities beyond academia, some also connect it to general diversification in researchers' careers, for instance, interdisciplinarity, internationality and issues of leadership. Thus, ideas of intersectorality are part of the initiatives' goals to increase diversity in items that are assessed both within and beyond academia.

In characterising the way diversity is important for them, many initiatives include areas which, in addition to research, encompass teaching, leadership, supervision, societal interaction and impact. For instance, ANECA promotes the idea that the ability to lead teaching and research teams and the education, training and mentoring of young teachers and researchers, should be part of considering promotion to professor level. Some more specific diversity considerations that are important for many initiatives include datasets and software as research outputs, teamwork during research activities, multilingualism, data management as well as collaboration with non-academic

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stakeholders. The variety of specific considerations and categories are presented below (box 1).

Box 1. Diversity related considerations and categories in research assessment

While these initiatives aim to promote diversity in academic career assessment, they do *not* expect researchers to excel in every area. Instead, the goal is to expand the range of contributions that could be considered in assessments.

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Many initiatives endeavour to give better recognition to diverse career roles, including data stewardship/curation, software engineering, science communication and science advice. Nearly all initiatives look to recognise and support diversity in career-paths (DORA is an exception since its focus lies elsewhere). In this context, diversity means primarily that researchers could advance in their careers through various activities and contributions, developing their competencies in line with their interests. However, the specific approaches to support the diversification of careers differ markedly among initiatives. Intersectoral mobility is often a key consideration.

The EU Charter focuses on the responsibility of employers and funders to encourage and support geographical, disciplinary, sectoral, and interorganizational mobility and combinations of simultaneous employment in different sectors (non-linear, multi-career and hybrid paths). According to the initiative, these should also be fully recognised and considered on par with a linear career path in assessment contexts.

YUFE4Postdocs emphasises the importance for early career researchers of skills and networks both for research and societal stakeholder related issues (diversity as competencies that go beyond traditional academic ones). CoARA's agreement and the Coalition include the recognition of diverse career-paths as an integral feature.

The Netherlands' initiative emphasises that academics should have a say in how they are assessed and given the opportunity to develop new career pathways. It promotes sharing of good practices, experimenting and fostering good leadership.

Norway's NOR-CAM addresses career-path diversity through a flexible framework that is applicable across disciplines, professional fields and the arts. It also considers leadership and impact.

Some initiatives support diversity of career-paths especially through wider considerations of researchers' contributions, activities and competencies in assessment (ANECA, CLACSO-FOLEC, Finland). A few also consider the issue of parental leave as important. They underline that fair assessment should take into account equality and family responsibilities.

UKRI focuses on supporting early career researchers' and technicians' engagement in various decision-contexts that deal with the development of the higher education sector. The initiative also connects this to recognising their contributions in these policy and strategy arenas. UKRI collaborates with various stakeholders and engages with research organisations to gain evidence-base that helps identify how technical careers can be supported and highlights gaps for intervention.

Finally, OR4 acknowledges that a researcher's ability to engage in open research may depend on their career path, among other factors. It advocates for these considerations to be incorporated into assessment practices.

6. Versatile tools for academic career assessment – guiding documents, databases and digital services

All the initiatives include tools for reforming academic career assessment, offering a range of guiding documents, databases and digital services for both evaluators and those being assessed. [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#), which underpins CoARA, includes a collection of practical tools that can support organisations in working towards the commitments of responsible research assessment (page 17).

The initiatives' guiding documents include varied tools, some of which offer directly applicable content for assessment situations. For instance, ANECA and Finland have developed CV templates, while DORA has published tips for using narrative CVs in evaluation. Similarly, Norway's NOR-CAM offers a holistic approach to career assessment with a template for diverse evaluation purposes.

Most of the guiding material include principles, recommendations and rubrics to inform and develop assessment processes. The EU Charter has produced a framework to support the recognition and evaluation of researchers' diverse competencies. Some guidelines developed by the initiatives focus on ethics of evaluation (ANECA) and responsible conduct of research (Finland), while others are more system-specific guides. These include guides for using DORA databases (DORA), the Finnish publication forum (Finland) and a technical guide for HR excellence in research reward (EU Charter). The Netherlands' Recognition and Rewards programme has also published a practical step-by-step plan to support institutions in initiating discussions with academics on career assessment, including suggestions for session format and a guide for moderators.

DORA, Finland and OR4 have developed self-reflection materials to help organisations assess and improve their existing practices. Finland's self-evaluation tool, linked to the Finnish Policy for Open Scholarship, includes measures and a checklist to promote openness of evaluation, learning, research data and publishing. In a similar vein, OR4's self-assessment helps institutions in evaluating the level of maturity in developing the recognition and rewarding of open research. DORA's SPACE tool and related workshop material support institutions in reflecting on their conditions to support the development and implementation of fair and responsible academic assessment. DORA has also published tips for evaluators of funding proposals and Ideas for Action, which debunks five common myths about research evaluation and offers five design principles to help institutions improve their research assessment practices.

For informational purposes, DORA has released a set of short documents (briefs) explaining impact and biases in evaluation. The EU Charter has produced several brochures covering various research assessment themes. Other informative resources include frequently asked questions (ANECA, DORA). Furthermore, CLACSO-FOLEC reported its principles and UKRI its action plan as their tools.

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Several initiatives have also developed databases and digital services to support their work. DORA's database Reformscape provides for openly available responsible research assessment policies, practices, and processes across academic institutions. The initiative also offers a collection of detailed case studies on responsible research assessment reform across a wide range of organisations. Finland's Ministry of Education and Culture operates the Research.fi service, which provides comprehensive information on diverse research outputs from research organisations, and facilitates the creation of researcher profiles and CVs based on the TENK CV template. ANECA has established a platform to gather feedback and input from stakeholders affected by its activities. Similarly, the Netherlands' initiative has a platform where participating organisations can ask questions and exchange practical advice.

7. Implementation and uptake of the initiatives

The initiatives take a systematic approach to implementation, with most having strategies and action plans for carrying out their activities and reaching their goals. Many have established committees or other responsible entities to support the implementation process. Relatedly, these initiatives encourage their signatories to create organisation-specific action plans and/or to commit to specific actions. For instance, DORA's policy asks signatory organisations to make a public statement explaining their commitment to DORA and to engage in ongoing dialogue with staff and students involved in research and research-enabling activities. Similarly, CoARA signatories commit to implementing its 10 commitments and must demonstrate progress in reforming research assessment processes within five years.

Most initiatives actively engage stakeholders through events, discussions and knowledge-sharing networks. They also maintain a list of signatories and emphasise collaboration as a means of fostering mutual learning, tool development and best practice sharing. The Netherlands' initiative, for instance, has conducted numerous experiments and discussions among stakeholders to put their Recognition & Rewards programme's principles into practice.

Training and guidance for evaluators is an important part of some initiatives' implementation process (ANECA, Finland, Norway). Norway's initiative has created a forum for institutions to learn about implementing the NOR-CAM framework. University technicians and scientific libraries were fundamental for ANECA's implementation process since they worked on open science and resolved many of the candidates' doubts about the new metrics, recommended sources of information and narrative CVs.

All the initiatives have made significant progress in uptake, illustrated by the amount of signatories and by the changes made in these organisations. For instance, ANECA anticipates over 16,000 applications per year under the new academic career assessment system. Norway's NOR-CAM is already being implemented locally by multiple organisations. As of January 2025, CoARA has attracted 817 signatories and 716 coalition members. Based on their interviews with each

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Recognition & Rewards project leader or HR policy advisor, The Netherlands' initiative found that all institutions are in the process of creating dynamic differentiation in academics' career paths. While some of these institutions are still in the development phase, others are already implementing career paths and/or profiles.

The initiatives also facilitate further uptake of their ideas. For instance, CLACSO-FOLEC incentivizes the implementation process through diverse mobilization actions, co-producing and sharing tools for designing responsible assessment policies and participating in research on research projects. DORA has clarified signatory expectations through its recent policy update and it encourages organisations to share their reform efforts via its resource library, case studies, or Reformscape. OR4 aims to use the CoARA national chapter as a forum to engage institutions not yet involved.

On the other hand, with relevance also to other initiatives, ANECA underlines that creating cultural change takes time. Their view is that while progress has been made, the objectives of responsible research assessment have not yet been fully realised, and the community has not yet to take full ownership of the process.

8. Encountering similar challenges and making gradual progress

The initiatives' responses reflect a variety of benefits and challenges. When it comes to the **benefits** from the implementation of the initiatives, two shared themes emerge.

- Firstly, most initiatives underline the way they have **sparked and enhanced cultural change**. Many have enabled the development of assessment approaches committed to equality, transparency and quality, recognising and rewarding diverse contributions, activities, competencies and career-paths through more qualitative judgement. For instance, ANECA has opened and driven the debate on research and academic career assessment in Spain, while the EU Charter fosters a more inclusive and unified research community, since it acknowledges common challenges across countries and recognises PhD researchers as professionals.
- The second benefit from the initiatives refer to the **active and diverse participation from academics**, which enhances the ownership of reforms and ensures that the experiences, expertise and needs of the targeted community are taken into account. For instance, CLACSO-FOLEC, which encompasses a broad scope of countries, emphasises that local participation and contextualization is essential to facilitate relevant and effective reform.

Initiatives such as Norway NOR-CAM and YUFE4Postdocs describe their benefits in terms of stakeholders or targeted institutions. Since NOR-CAM caters both to institutions that are more cautious and those who want to move faster or work in a different way, it is being received well in Norway. The participating universities of YUFE4Postdocs have gained experience with qualitative assessment. Furthermore, the initiative resulted in contacts, and potential for collaboration with societal stakeholders, most of them situated in the ecosystems of the participating universities. Relatedly, Finland's initiative underlines that it helped to prepare the Finnish research community, at a policy level, to become early adopters of the CoARA agreement.

Finally, some initiatives also emphasise broader societal benefits. ANECA's new evaluation model can be beneficial for citizens, as it decisively promotes open science and citizen science. Similarly, OR4 highlights that its activities benefit both researchers and the wider society, as it should increase the accessibility, reproducibility and re-usability of research.

However, the initiatives have also encountered some shared **challenges**:

- First, assessment reforms require a **major cultural change across complex research ecosystems**. The amount of diverse stakeholders involved in the process contribute to a slower implementation process and require a lot of concerted and codirectional action between different organisations. At the same time, reform processes must also ensure that institutions have adequate autonomy in designing their assessment approaches.
- Second, **resource constraints** pose difficulties. ANECA and YUFE4Postdocs stress the need for investments in training and guidance for evaluators. Similarly, CoARA highlights that maintaining and promoting the work around academic career assessment takes a lot of time and effort. Relatedly, DORA notes that as reforms are often driven and initiated locally by individuals, there is a need to develop more practical resources for such community champions.
- Third, **transitioning to new assessment models**. While diversity in assessment may have increased, legacy valuation systems regarding career-paths persist, making career progression criteria and paths seem unfamiliar and unclear to researchers.
- Four, the **subjective nature of qualitative assessment** presents challenges. While quantitative metrics, while lacking in many ways, have traditionally been seen as objective, some academics question whether qualitative evaluation can be conducted in a fair and unbiased manner. Relatedly, The Netherlands' initiative noted that stakeholders have reported difficulty in designing qualitative criteria for assessing individuals within teams.

Additional challenges specific to certain initiatives include difficulties faced by smaller institutions in supporting diverse career paths (Netherlands) and increasing demand for peer-reviewers (YUFE4Postdocs).

It should be noted that challenges are inevitable when reforming systems and cultures at national or international level and sharing experiences and insights is crucial. While reforms take time, initiatives continue working towards more inclusive and responsible career assessment, better recognising and supporting diversity in academia and responsible use of metrics and qualitative assessment. Given the commitment from several stakeholders, the next steps could include closely following up on the progress made by the initiatives and sharing future contributions across initiatives to drive further improvement.

Links to initiatives' websites and documents

Further information about the initiatives can be found in their websites or from their documentation. The list below covers links to central pages and/or documents on each of the case initiatives.

ANECA:

- [Proceso para la reforma de la evaluación de la investigación](#)
- [Process for reforming research evaluation](#)
- [El CVA ANECA](#) -pdf

CLACSO-FOLEC:

- [Declaracion de principios](#) -pdf
- [Declaration of principles](#) -pdf

CoARA:

- [About CoARA](#)
- [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#)

DORA:

- [Homepage DORA](#)
- [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment](#)
- [Reformscape](#)
- [Case studies on reforming research assessment](#)
- [A practical guide for research evaluators](#)
- [A rubric for analyzing institutional conditions and progress indicators](#)
- [Building Blocks for Impact](#)
- [Debiasing Committee Composition and Deliberative Processes](#)

Eu Charter:

- [The European Charter for Researchers](#) -pdf
- [The European Charter & Code for Researchers](#)

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- [ERA Talent Platform](#)
- [HR Excellence in Research Award](#)

Finland:

- [Responsible Assessment](#)
- [Good Practice in Researcher Evaluation. Recommendation for the Responsible Evaluation of a Researcher in Finland.](#) -pdf
- [Researcher's Curriculum Vitae Template](#) -pdf

The Netherlands:

- [Recognition & Rewards homepage](#)
- [Summary of Recognition & Rewards plan](#) -pdf
- [Room for everyone's talent](#) -pdf
- [Room for everyone's talent in practice](#)
- [Toolkit for Dialogue](#) -pdf

Norway:

- [Vurdering av akademiske karrierer](#)
- [NOR-CAM – A toolbox for recognition and rewards in academic careers](#)

OR4:

- [Homepage OR4](#)
- [Open and Responsible Researcher Reward and Recognition Working Group \(OR4\): Project Plan](#)
- [A toolkit for recognising and rewarding open research](#)

UKRI:

- [Homepage UKRI People and Teams action plan](#)
- [People and Teams UKRI action plan](#) -pdf

YUFE4Postdocs:

- [About YUFE4Postdocs](#)
- [YUFE4Postdocs call](#)

